

The INRAM Protocol for Georeferencing Biological Museum Specimen Records

Version 1.3

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1.0 Goals and General Procedures

The Institute for Natural Resource Analysis and Management (INRAM) has undertaken an effort to database and georeference the biological museum collections from Eastern New Mexico University (ENMU), New Mexico State University (NMSU), the Museum of Southwestern Biology (MSB) at the University of New Mexico (UNM) and Western New Mexico University (WNMU). This document presents our goals and proposed general procedures for georeferencing these museum collections. Our process has been to analyze the procedures of other georeferencing projects, particularly that of the Mammal Networked Information System (MaNIS), and produce a methodology that is as good or better than those attempted to date.

“Georeferencing” is the process of expressing a terrestrial spatial description in coordinates within a frame of reference (Wieczorek and Beaman 2002). An acceptably georeferenced specimen record includes sufficient information to place a uniquely identified collection event within a coordinate system with a frame of reference and an extent (Frazier 2003). In practice, such a record consists of a point, which represents our best estimate as to the location of the collection event, and an extent, which represents our cumulative uncertainty in ascertaining the exact location of the collection event.

The INRAM Georeferencing project will assign to the NM biological museum specimens latitude and longitude estimates expressed as decimal degrees to a five-digit precision using the World Geodetic System 1984 datum.

Our approach to assigning extent is to initially review specimen records and classify them based on the type of locality information they contain. Each class will have its own rules for how to determine best estimate for the location of the collection event. In addition, each class will have its own rules for how to determine the uncertainty associated with the assigned location. All precision estimates will be presented as the radius (in meters, m) from the geographic point assigned in the georeferencing process.

To georeference specimen records, INRAM will use standard geographic referencing data in an ArcGIS software environment. Additional tools have been developed using Visual Basic scripts and ArcObject models for the ArcGIS ArcMap interface.

The tools and procedures being developed by the INRAM georeferencing project were designed to assign locality information to existing museum records as efficiently and accurately as possible. These tools and procedures are also designed to facilitate georeferencing of new specimen records as they come in. INRAM recognizes that the future of museum workflow includes the need for standardized georeferencing tools and procedures to accompany the daily accessioning of information. Using these tools and procedures, museum staff can become more comfortable with geospatial data and concepts and can have more control over the quality of their collection information.

In the next section of this document, Section 2.0, Data Preparation, we provide the steps that the individual division or museum will need to follow in order to prepare their data for georeferencing. Section 3.0, Hierarchy of Precision, provides a framework for deciding the type

of locality information that contains the most precise information to use in the georeferencing process. If the museum has a hierarchy of preference, we will use it instead of the one suggested here. Section 4.0 contains information on how to assign a “georeferencing category” to a locality description, along with rules for determining the uncertainty associated with each category. Section 5.0 illustrates the type of data and format the contributing museum will receive post georeference processing. Section 6.0 is a diagram of the workflow for the georeferencing project. Section 7.0 contains the structure and design of the Access database for maintenance of the georeferenced data. References are included in Section 8.0.

2.0 Data Preparation

The following is a list of the fields that are required for INRAM to georeference museum data for New Mexico. An explanation of required fields and formats follow column headings that are shown below within brackets ‘[]’. These column headings should be used in any spreadsheet or database version of data submitted to the georeferencing process to facilitate integration with other records in the system. INRAM will accept data in Microsoft Excel, Microsoft Access, or tab delimited ascii file. There should be 18 fields in the data provided for georeferencing, shown below (*see* 2.2 and 2.3). Please note that we have selected the predominant coordinate systems and locality data that are typically used in New Mexico and have excluded fields for coordinate systems such as State Plane. This was done to limit the amount of data preparation required by the museum; however, information in alternate coordinate systems will be accepted, simply place those into the ‘text’ locality field (*see* 2.2, below).

2.1 Record and Collection Event Fields

2.1.1 *Museum [mus]*

For each record, assign a unique abbreviation to identify your collection. Official published abbreviations for museums (e.g.: MSB for Museum of Southwestern Biology or UNM for the UNM herbarium) are not sufficient to distinguish different collections within an institute (for example the MSB Herpetology division from the Mammal division). INRAM will work with collection managers to determine appropriate unique identifiers. (Field Type: Text)

2.1.2 *Unique record ID [id]*

A unique numeric ID for a record. This unique ID will allow you to associate completed georeferenced data to your collection’s database. (Field Type: Numeric)

2.1.3 *Date of Collection [coldate]*

The date recorded for the collection event. Preferred format of the date field is: YYYY-MM-DD. This field is useful in cases where time-dependent locality information is given (for example, the locality is given as Valencia, but at the time of the collection this county included what is now Cibola county. (Field Type: Date; however, we realize this may not be feasible, so Text will be accepted).

2.2 Locality Fields

At least *one* of the following locality fields must be provided for each record. Do not supply a record without at least one field populated. If you have a coordinate system that is not represented below in one of the fields provided (e.g. State Plane, Central Zone), place the information into the ‘locality’ field (i.e. 2.2.3 Text [locality]).

2.2.1 State [st]

This field is included for future expansion to include other states. Place ‘NM’ for New Mexico. (Field Type: Text)

2.2.2 County [co]

If known, the county in New Mexico where the specimen was collected. This field is useful in differentiating place names that are redundant in the state. Make sure that the county names are spelled correctly and that the counties listed for New Mexico records are, in fact, in New Mexico. There are 33 counties in New Mexico. (Field Type: Text)

2.2.3 Text [locality]

This field should contain a description concerning the geographic locality of a collection event. Ancillary information (e.g. habitat, morphology, associated species, weather info, etc.) should be removed from this field. (Field Type: Text)

2.2.4 Longitude [long]

This field is used for collection events for which longitude was recorded. Acceptable units include (1) degree minute second, (2) decimal degree, or (3) degree decimal minute. The format for (1) should be –106 35 14, (2) should be –106.58722, (3) should be –10635.2333. Note that all longitudes west of Greenwich Meridian are negative. (Field Type: Text)

2.2.5 Latitude [lat]

This field is used for collection events for which latitude was recorded. Acceptable units include (1) degree minute second, (2) decimal degree, or (3) degree decimal minute. The format for (1) should be 33 24 15, (2) should be 33.404166, (3) should be 3324.25. Note that all latitudes north of the equator are positive. (Field Type: Text)

2.2.6 Datum_LL [datum_ll]

If Longitude/Latitude coordinates were recorded for a collection event, this is the frame of reference for those coordinates, if known. In most cases we expect the North American Datum 1927 (NAD27). For more recent collections, using a GPS, we may have the North American Datum 1983 (NAD83), or the World Geodetic System (WGS84). (Field Type: Text)

2.2.7 UTM Easting [utme]

This field is used for coordinates derived from the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection. For New Mexico, this field has 6-digits for the easting. Make sure the ‘zone’ field is filled out (see below), if known. (Field Type: Numeric)

2.2.8 UTM Northing [utmn]

This field is used for coordinates derived from the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) projection. For New Mexico, this field has 7-digits for the northing. Make sure the 'zone' field is filled out (see below), if known. (Field Type: Numeric)

2.2.9 Zone [zone]

Zone is only filled in for coordinates that were derived from the UTM projection. For New Mexico, this will be either '12' or '13'. Zone 12 begins in Arizona and ends at the 108° longitude in New Mexico. Zone 12 encompasses much of the western counties that include: Hidalgo, Grant, Catron, Cibola, McKinley, and San Juan. Of this group of counties, only Hidalgo is completely within zone 12. Input a zone only if you are confident which zone was used for the UTM coordinates. It is possible to reproject a coordinate into a different zone using a GIS. In some cases the data in Zone 12 has already been reprojected into zone 13. The reprojection becomes evident when UTM coordinates for areas west of longitude 108° in New Mexico ranges approximately from 115000E to 130000E. Again, if you do not know the zone, do not add it to the field. (Field Type: Numeric)

2.2.10 Datum UTM [datum_utm]

If UTM coordinates were recorded for a collection event, this is the frame of reference for those coordinates, if known. In most cases we expect the North American Datum 1927 (NAD27). For more recent collections, using a GPS, we may have the North American Datum 1983 (NAD83), or the World Geodetic System (WGS84). (Field Type: Text)

2.2.11 Township [town]

Township for the public land survey system. The format for this field will include a 'T' and number followed by 'N' or 'S' (for example, 'T25N'). If the number is a single digit, place a '0' in front of the number. (Field Type: Text)

2.2.12 Range [range]

Range for the public land survey system. The format for this field will include an 'R' and number followed by 'E' or 'W'. If the number is a single digit, place a '0' in front of the number (for example, 'R11E'). (Field Type: Text)

2.2.13 Section [section]

Section number for the township and range public land survey system. The range of numbers is 1-36. At times the section will not be given, only the township and range. (Field Type: Numeric)

2.2.14 Quarters and comments [qtr]

The half to quarter section designations, along with comments about the public land survey system can be included in this field (for example, 'N/2, SW/4'). This would be the north-half of the southwest quarter of the section. (Field Type: Text)

2.2.15 Original Coordinate System [Orig]

A description of the original coordinate system used to determine the point of reference for a record. Appropriate examples would be: UTM or LONG/LAT or TRS or LOCALITY. Locality refers to textual locality information in the absence of coordinates. (Field Type: Text)

2.3 Nomenclatural Fields

The fields listed below will be used to help standardize and expedite the georeference processing. For example, a collection from Heron Lake would be georeferenced as occurring in the lake if it were a catfish, while that of a cottonwood would be placed on its shore. Records that have not been identified at least to the level of Family should not be submitted for georeferencing.

2.3.1 Plant or Animal [p_a]

Whether the record is for a plant (p) or animal (a). (Field Type: Text)

2.3.2 Family [family]

This field is for the family name for each record. (Field Type: Text)

2.3.3 Scientific Name [sciname]

If your database contains the scientific name as one field, e.g. not separated into a separate genus and species field, use this field for the taxon name, if you chose to give this information. If for data sensitivity reasons, you would rather not provide the whole scientific name, please provide the genus. (Field Type: Text)

2.3.4 Genus [genus]

This field is for the genus name, if known, for each record. (Field Type: Text)

3.0 Priority of Location Information

To expedite the georeferencing process, submitted records will be categorized by the type of locality information they include. For records that contain more than one form of reference (e.g. UTM and longitude/latitude information), only one type of reference will be used in the initial georeferencing. Preference will be given to the original coordinate system, if known (*see* 2.2.15). Locality information will be used for georeferencing with the following priority:

1. Longitude/Latitude
2. UTM
3. PLSS
4. Specific description
5. County
6. State

Thus, for example, if a record includes Long/Lat coordinates, any included UTM or PLSS data will not be used for the initial georeferencing, unless the UTM is the original source. The locality descriptions will be used only if no coordinates are provided. If a record contains neither

coordinates nor mappable locality description, the record will be mapped to the county or, if no county is given, the state centroid.

To some degree, this ranking of priority is arbitrary; for instance, there is no reason to suppose that Long/Lat data are more accurate than UTM data. At some point, the totality of locality information contained in the record must be addressed and a better georeferencing applied to records with multiple types of locality information. This priority is intended only to facilitate the rapid initial georeferencing of the record. If for a given collection, there is a priori knowledge that a different priority would generate more accurate results, this should be addressed when the records are sent to the georeferencing team.

4.0 Locality Information Categories

Collection event records will be categorized according to the type of locality information they contain. To this end, we developed a table classifying localities (Table 1). The categorizing of localities serves multiple purposes. First, for many categories, uncertainty can be assigned automatically or with a semi-automated process. For some categories future GIS integration could be implemented to generate the uncertainty or representation of the location and eliminate the need for ad hoc determination of uncertainty with each collection record. For example, some localities could be linked directly to a GIS (e.g. Bernalillo Co., NM) and represented as polygons. In other cases, the uncertainty could be derived as a complex polygon. For example, a location along a road between two known features could have its uncertainty represented as an offset along a line between the two feature points.

Categorization also makes the georeferencing process more efficient and accurate. During a given georeferencing session, the georeferencer can be assigned records that all require the same process for determining the locality and uncertainty. Records that require a more elaborate effort to georeference and which require more deliberation to assign locality and uncertainty estimates can be separated from those requiring less effort. More knowledgeable and able staff can be assigned to the more difficult categories of records, while inexperienced or lower-level staff can address the more simple records.

In Table 1, the categories are arranged in the order they might be addressed during the categorization process. Category A records (those with coordinates) are assigned dynamically and are processed separately from the rest. The remaining categories may be assigned by a manager prior to the georeferencing effort or they may be applied by the georeferencing staff during the process. The Type Localities K and L are the products of the most deliberation. K records fall out when the information as given cannot be used for georeferencing due to some type of internal discrepancy. The L category is a catch-all for records that require more elaborate judgments to be made before they can be georeferenced. The following subsections give more detail concerning each of the georeferencing categories.

Table 1. Locality Types and Uncertainty Estimates

Locality Type [lcid]	Description of the locality information type	Examples	Georeferencing procedure	Uncertainty estimate
A	Coordinates given (L/L, UTM, PLSS)	34° 55.43' N, 107° 65.32' W; T13S R3E Sec3	Use GIS tools to convert to common output.	See Table 2
B	Only vague information given	Under rock near big house	Mapped to state or, if given, county. Otherwise unmappable.	That of the state or, if given, the county. Otherwise not calculated.
C	Questionable locality (question mark used or other uncertainty modifier)	Santa Fe?; Maybe Hillsboro.	Same as for B	Same as for B
D	Single named place (either a GNIS named place or an intersection, e.g. road or river or other)	Las Cruces, NM; Black Well (feature), Socorro Co., NM OR intersection of I-20 and NM115	Use GNIS of named place to establish coordinates. Do not create duplicate point in GIS layer.	Apply uncertainty estimate associated with the GNIS feature or intersection ¹
E	Vague description of a single named place (either a GNIS named place or an intersection, e.g. road or river or other)	E of Socorro; near Animas OR SE of the intersection of I-20 and NM115	Same as for D. Do not create duplicate point in GIS layer.	Same as for D
F	Offset distance from a single named place (either a GNIS named place or an intersection, e.g. road or river or other)	5 mi from Farmington	Use customized GNIS toolbar and ArcGIS Editor tools to determine coordinates.	A radius consisting of uncertainty in distance measure + calculated GNIS uncertainty for feature
G	Qualifier with distance from single named place (either a GNIS named place or an intersection, e.g. road or river or other)	About 4 km from Taos	Use customized GNIS toolbar and ArcGIS Editor tools to determine point.	Twice radius as calculated in F
H	Direction, distance and named place OR two orthogonal offsets from a single named place (either a GNIS named place or an intersection, e.g. road or river or other) (either a GNIS named place or an intersection, e.g. road or river or other)	5.2 mi SE of Belen OR 2 mi S of Belen and 1 mi E (may be an intersection of roads or rivers)	Use GNIS of named place and distance by air to determine coordinates with ArcGIS Editor tools.	A radius consisting of uncertainty in distance measure + calculated GNIS uncertainty for feature + calculated cardinal direction

¹ The intersection of a road, stream, or other identifiable landmark is a predetermined radius of 15m. This offset is used in Type Localities D-I, where chosen in the database. If the GNIS radius is undetermined, either a -888 or -999 has been placed in the field. A -888 signifies more work can be done to determine a radius. A -999 means a radius probably cannot be determined, e.g. Otero Mesa. The boundaries of this mesa are open to interpretation.

Locality Type [lcid]	Description of the locality information type	Examples	Georeferencing procedure	Uncertainty estimate
I	Direction, distance by road or other vector (river, boundary) and single named place OR two orthogonal offsets from a single named place (either a GNIS named place or an intersection, e.g. road or river or other)	8 km by road E of Hillsboro OR 2 mi S of Belen by road and 1 mi E on Hwy 387 (may be an intersection of roads or rivers)	Use GNIS of named place and ArcGIS <i>Traverse</i> to establish coordinates. Use <i>Traverse</i> for two or more orthogonal offsets.	A radius consisting of uncertainty in distance measure + calculated GNIS uncertainty for feature or intersection
J	A vague description concerning two or more known features	Between Bernardo and Mountainair	Assign point to midpoint of features using <i>Distance-Distance</i> tool in Editor toolbar.	Radius from midpoint to farthest feature
K	Contradictions within location information.	Las Cruces, Colfax County (Las Cruces is in Dona Ana County)	Do not map	No calculation
L	Mappable, but does not fit above categories. Complex descriptions including reference to multiple features with different degrees of uncertainty.	Water Canyon about 2 miles from campground.	Map and provide notes	Assign estimated uncertainty and provide notes
M	Unmappable	Various, determined by transcriber	Unmappable, provide notes	No calculation

4.1 Type A Locality

The locality data provided for this type is Longitude/Latitude, UTM, or PLSS (Public Lands Survey System). Type A data will be processed by the Georeferencing Project Administrator and sorted by the priority of coordinate systems as given in section 3.0. The data will be projected into a common coordinate system, mapped in a GIS, and have a standard uncertainty estimate attached to the point. Uncertainty estimates are given to maximize the accuracy of the data. Since we are using a point to represent the locality of a specimen that was collected from within an area (PLSS data), we will need to identify the uncertainty associated with the point. For others, such as no record of a datum, the error associated with this can be from tens to hundreds of meters off of the intended precision offered by the X,Y coordinate. The uncertainty estimates are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Uncertainty Estimates for Type A Localities

SubType	Qualifier	Format Example	Uncertainty Estimate (m)	Rationale see below table
Long/Lat	Datum unknown	DDD.ddddd; DDDMM.mmmm; DMS	200	(1)
Long/Lat	Datum unknown	DM (no seconds)	2000	(2)
Long/Lat	Datum known, before 1 May 2000	DDD.ddddd; DDDMM.mmmm; DMS	100	(3)
Long/Lat	Datum known, after 1 May 2000	DDD.ddddd; DDDMM.mmmm; DMS	30	(4)
UTM	Datum unknown	X,Y	200	(5)
UTM	Datum known, before 1 May 2000	X,Y	100	(6)
UTM	Datum known, after 1 May 2000	X,Y	30	(7)
PLSS	Township	T6SR14E	6828	(8)
PLSS	Section	T6S R14E Sec. 23	1138	(9)
PLSS	¼ Section	T6N R14E Sec. 23 NE 1/4	570	(10)
PLSS	¼ of ¼ Section	T6N R14E Sec. 23 NE 1/4 SW 1/4	285	(11)
PLSS	¼ of ¼ of ¼ Section	T6N R14E Sec. 23 NW 1/4 NE 1/4 SW 1/4	143	(12)

- (1) GNIS points for New Mexico were projected into both NAD27 and NAD83 and used in a GIS to determine the distance between points. The average offset was 208 m. (Neville, T., pers. comm.)
- (2) Without the precision of seconds, minute precision in New Mexico is approximately 1.8 km.
- (3) Assuming the coordinates were derived from a GPS, from 25 March 1990 to 1 May 2000, Selective Availability (SA) was the purposeful degradation of the GPS signal for civilian users. This took the form of a timing offset in the signals coming from the satellites giving

a slightly erroneous position (up to 100m radius for 95% of the time, Dana 1999). Software was commercially available to differentially correct for the offset, but unless a note is attached to the collection record regarding correction for SA, we assume the maximum error. Differentially corrected GPS data are 1-10 meters in accuracy (Dana 1999).

- (4) Without SA the error is about a radius of 30m. If the data are differentially corrected, the error can be 2-3 m (Dana 1999).
- (5) GNIS points for New Mexico were projected into both NAD27 and NAD83 and used in a GIS to determine the distance between points. The average offset was 208 m.
- (6) Assuming the coordinates were derived from a GPS, from 25 March 1990 to 1 May 2000, Selective Availability (SA) was the purposeful degradation of the GPS signal for civilian users. This took the form of a timing offset in the signals coming from the satellites giving a slightly erroneous position (up to 100m radius for 95% of the time, Dana 1999). Software was commercially available to differentially correct for the offset, but unless a note is attached to the collection record regarding correction for SA, we assume the maximum error. Differentially corrected GPS data are 1-10 meters in accuracy (Dana 1999).
- (7) Without SA the error is about a radius of 30m. If the data are differentially corrected, the error can be 2-3 m (Dana 1999).
- (8) The size of a township is 6 mi x 6 mi. The error is calculated as half the distance of the hypotenuse of an isosceles right triangle. $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$; error = $\text{sqrt } c^2/2$.
- (9) The size of a section is 1 mi x 1 mi. See (8).
- (10) The size of a 1/4 section is 0.5 mi x 0.5 mi. See (8).
- (11) The size of a 1/4 of a 1/4 section is 0.25 mi x 0.25 mi. See (8).
- (12) The size of a 1/4 of a 1/4 of a 1/4 section is 0.125 mi x 0.125 mi. See (8).

4.2 Type B Locality

Only vague information is provided in the locality field. Some of these may include features that cannot be found (e.g. under rock near big house) using available GIS data. It may be mapped to the state or, if given, county, otherwise, it is unmappable. If the record is mapped to the county or state, the uncertainty estimate is calculated as for type D localities.

4.3 Type C Locality

If the only information given in the locality field is a single questionable locality (e.g. Santa Fe? or "Maybe Hillsboro") it should be treated as if there is no information in this field. It may be mapped to the state or, if given, county, otherwise, it is unmappable. If the record is mapped to the county or state, the uncertainty estimate is calculated as for type D localities.

4.4 Type D Locality

A single feature name is given without any distance or direction measurements. All GNIS features will be assigned an uncertainty estimate that will be included as an attribute in the feature place names (FPN) GIS layer. For features for which we can obtain a polygon (e.g. lakes, towns, cities, counties), a radius will be calculated from the area of the polygon. This

radius will be the uncertainty estimate. The set of procedures and calculations for the radius for the GNIS features that have polygons are as follows:

The center of mass for individual polygons (MassX, MassY) and the maximum x and y (MaxX, MaxY) of the polygons were extracted using visual basic scripts in ArcGIS (Tchoukanski 2003). The difference between the center and maximums (MaxX – MassX) and (MaxY – MassY) were used to determine the radius: $\text{Sqrt}((\text{MaxX} - \text{MassX})^2 + (\text{MaxY} - \text{MassY})^2)$.

All other features will be assigned an arbitrary uncertainty estimate appropriate to each feature or feature type. The feature type is designated in the GNIS table, examples include: mine, historical marker, windmill, etc. For New Mexico, the uncertainty estimate given for these examples is 15 m. Large mines were exempted from the arbitrary uncertainty estimate; their errors were calculated separately using photo interpretive techniques by measuring the mine disturbance in satellite imagery. A GIS layer of the polygons can be used in a GIS to link to the database records.

If the feature is not a designated FPN but is an identifiable place such as an intersection, e.g. road and road, stream and stream, road and stream, etc., the uncertainty estimate used to calculate the intersection is 15 m. If the GNIS radius is undetermined, either a –888 or –999 has been placed in the field. A –888 signifies more work can be done to determine a radius. A –999 means a radius probably cannot be determined, e.g. Otero Mesa. The boundaries of this mesa are open to interpretation.

4.5 Type E Locality

A vague description is given for a single named place with no other location information. The direction might state that the collection was made ‘east of Albuquerque’. We are not given a unit of measure for distance from a named location so we need to attach an uncertainty estimate. The uncertainty estimate for Type E will be the same as for Type D.

If the feature is not a designated FPN but is an identifiable place such as an intersection, e.g. road and road, stream and stream, road and stream, etc., the uncertainty estimate used to calculate the intersection is 15 m.

4.6 Type F Locality

The distance is known but the direction is unknown for a single named locality (e.g. 5 mi from Farmington). The locality could be assigned as a circle at the distance from the feature place name location. In practice, it will be assigned the coordinates of the FPN. The uncertainty estimate will be calculated to include both the uncertainty associated with the GNIS feature place name (see 4.4, Type D Locality) and the uncertainty associated the distance measure. The uncertainty associated with the distance measure is calculated using rules of significant digits. Thus, the uncertainty on “12 mi” is plus or minus 1 mile; on “10.1” mi it is plus or minus 0.1 miles. We consider multiples of 10 miles to be, on average, less precise distance estimates with the uncertainty dependent on the distance value. The rule for determining the uncertainty estimate for multiples of 10 is that it is 15% of the distance value. Thus the uncertainty estimate for “10 miles” is 1.5 miles, for 30 miles it is 4.5 miles, for 75 miles, it is 11.25 miles. The same rule would be applied to distances measured in kilometers.

If the feature is not a designated FPN but is an identifiable place such as an intersection, e.g. road and road, stream and stream, road and stream, etc., the uncertainty estimate used to calculate the intersection is 15 m.

4.7 Type G Locality

A qualifier such as ‘about’ or ‘approximately’ precedes the distance from a single feature place (e.g. About 4 km from Taos). The direction is not given. The uncertainty estimate is twice that of Type F Locality, see 4.6.

If the feature is not a designated FPN but is an identifiable place such as an intersection, e.g. road and road, stream and stream, road and stream, etc., the uncertainty estimate used to calculate the intersection is 15 m.

4.8 Type H Locality

A simple direction with a distance measure from a named place is given (e.g. 3.2 mi SE of Morris Well) or two orthogonal offsets from a single named place (2 mi S of Belen and 1 mi E). There is no indication on how the direction was derived (e.g. by air, by road) so we assume by air. Cardinal (e.g. N, S), primary intercardinal points (e.g. NE, SW) or secondary intercardinal points (e.g. NNE, SSW) will be used with distance from the FPN to generate the coordinates for this type of locality.

The uncertainty estimate will be generated as the maximum of the distance uncertainty estimate (see 4.6, Type F locality) and the direction uncertainty estimate (DUE) for that distance. The rule for calculating the DUE is:

If the direction is cardinal then the angle of error is 45°

If the direction is primary intercardinal then the angle of error is 22.5°

If the direction is secondary intercardinal then the angle of error is 11.25°

The radius of the DUE for a given distance is: $nDistance(\tan(\text{angle of error}))$.

If the feature is not a designated FPN but is an identifiable place such as an intersection, e.g. road and road, stream and stream, road and stream, etc., the uncertainty estimate used to calculate the intersection is 15 m.

4.9 Type I Locality

The direction and distance are specified by means of a defined vector such as a road, waterway, by air or boundary from a single place name (8 km by road east of Hillsboro) or two orthogonal offsets from a single named place (2 mi S of Belen by road and 1 mi E on Hwy 387). To assign the coordinates for this point, follow the specified vector for the distance specified from the FPN

in the GIS. The uncertainty is assigned as a function of the distance value and the uncertainty inherent in the FPN location as with Type F localities (Section 4.6).

If the feature is not a designated FPN but is an identifiable place such as an intersection, e.g. road and road, stream and stream, road and stream, etc., the uncertainty estimate used to calculate the intersection is 15 m.

4.10 Type J Locality

At least two features are given, no distances are provided (e.g. Along US 60 between Bernardo and Mountainair). Assign a point to the approximate mid-point of the features given. The uncertainty estimate is the distance from the midpoint to a furthest feature.

4.11 Type K Locality

The information provided contains internal discrepancies (e.g. Las Cruces, Colfax County). In this example we know that Las Cruces is in Doña Ana County and there is no Las Cruces in Colfax County. These records are not mapped in our process nor is an uncertainty estimate generated. These records should be sent back to the collection managers to determine if the error might have occurred in the data transcription process or if further review of the specimen data could resolve the discrepancy. If the nature of the discrepancy is obvious and can be clearly resolved, a K record may be changed to an L record and mapped.

4.12 Type L Locality

The information provided in the locality description does not fit any of the situations for Type A – Type K, but can still be reasonably mapped. These records will require more judgment and expertise to map than the ones from other categories. Typically, records would fall into this category because they reference multiple feature place names with varying precision. In these cases, the different pieces of information must be weighed to determine the best coordinates and uncertainty estimate. The georeferencer is given substantial latitude in how to georeference L records, however, notes must be kept detailing the process used.

It is likely that we will find that some processes are used repeatedly to georeference subsets of L records. In these cases, we will generate L subcategories to save the amount of effort required to document the georeferencing process.

4.13 Type M Locality

Any locality information that does not fit types A-L. The transcriber is unwilling to commit to a mappable locality.

5.0 Output to Museum, Post Processing

Table 3 includes the fields and a short description of the data to be provided back to contributing museums after the records are georeferenced. The DB-ID field indicates whether the values for that field were derived from the identity tools in ArcGIS (ID) or from the Access database (AD). For ID fields, the original format is a shapefile. For AC records, the Access database was used

to store the tabular data entered by the transcriber or, in some cases (e.g. Uncertainty), the values were calculated using formulas developed in the database. The data will be provided in an Access Database, unless otherwise specified.

Table 3. Output to Museum

DB-ID	Field Name	Description
ID/AC	RecID	Unique ID that links to the original museum database, GIS data, and Access database (concatenated with original ID)
ID/AC	ID	Unique ID from museum's original dataset
AC	Category	Locality category (e.g. A or B or C ... L)
ID	County	County in New Mexico where the coordinates were placed. May or may not be the same as the county as given with the original specimen record.
ID	Long84	Longitude in decimal degrees
ID	Lat84	Latitude in decimal degrees
ID	LLDatum	Datum - World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS84)
ID	X	Easting - UTM
ID	Y	Northing - UTM
ID	XYDatum	Datum - North American Datum 1927 (NAD27)
AC	Uncertainty	Uncertainty estimate in meters.
AC	Transcriber	Individual responsible for transcribing data, creating the locality information, and entering the data
AC	DateTrans	Date of transcription
AC	GNISID	Unique ID for the GNIS feature. Only used for categories D, E, F, G, H, and I.
AC	Intersection	Intersection of either road, river, or other. Only used for categories D, E, F, G, H, and I.
AC	Distance	Only used for Type Locality F, G, H, I.
AC	DistanceUnit	Only used for Type Locality F, G, H, I.
AC	Direction	Only used for Type Locality H or I
AC	Notes	Comment field
AC	Unid	Either -888 or -999. GNIS uncertainty qualifiers.
AC	Htable	Separate table: One-many relationship with master table

Table 4 is an example of the GNIS reference (lookup) table used to assign uncertainty estimates in meters for those locality categories that use FPN uncertainty estimates (D, E, F, G, H, and I).

Table 4. Lookup Table for GNIS Feature and Associated Error

GNISID	FName	FType	FCounty	FError
1	Barrel Spring	spring	Otero	15
2	Tohatchi	ppl	McKinley	3578.56
3	Kingston	ppl	Sierra	-888 ²
4	Zuni Plateau	area	Cibola	-999

² If the GNIS radius is undetermined, either a -888 or -999 has been placed in the field. A -888 signifies more work can be done to determine a radius. A -999 means a radius probably cannot be determined, e.g. Otero Mesa. The boundaries of this mesa are open to interpretation.

Table 5 is the reference (lookup) table on cardinal, intercardinal and secondary intercardinal directions used for calculation of the direction uncertainty estimate. NDir is the angle used for placing the coordinates. ADir is the angle used to determine the directional uncertainty estimate.

Table 5. Lookup Table for Cardinal Directions

TDir	NDir	ADir
N	0	45
NNE	23	11.25
NE	45	22.5
ENE	68	11.25
E	90	45
ESE	113	11.25
SE	135	22.5
SSE	158	11.25
S	180	45
SSW	203	11.25
SW	225	22.5
WSW	248	11.25
W	270	45
WNW	293	11.25
NW	315	22.5
NNW	338	11.25

6.0 Workflow

7.0 Design of Access Database

The Access database will hold the data described in Section 2.0, Data Preparation, as well as the calculated uncertainty estimates determined by the transcribers.

Table 6. Main Access Table

FieldName	Section	Type
mus	2.1.1	Text
id	2.1.2	Text
coldate	2.1.3	Date
locality	2.2.3	Text
long	2.2.4	Single precision
lat	2.2.5	Single precision
datum_ll	2.2.6	Drop down: NAD27, NAD83, WGS84
utme	2.2.7	Single precision
utm_n	2.2.8	Single precision
zone	2.2.9	Drop-down: 12 or 13
datum_utm	2.2.10	Drop down: NAD27, NAD83, WGS84
section	2.2.13	Integer
town	2.2.11	Text
range	2.2.12	Text
qtr	2.2.14	Text
co	2.2.2	Drop-down: NM Counties
st	2.2.1	Drop-down: US states
sciname	2.3.3	Text
family	2.3.2	Text
genus	2.3.4	Text
p_a	2.3.1	P or A
lcid	4.0, Table 1	A-M
uncertainty	5.0, Table 3	Meters (single precision)
dist_from	5.0, Table 3	Single precision
dist_unit	5.0, Table 3	Drop-down: km, meters, miles, feet
direction	5.0, Table 5	Drop-down: both degree & direction
notes	5.0, Table 3	Notes field

Table 7. Look up tables

Table Name	Table Reference	Notes
GNIS	Table 4	
Cardinal Direction	Table 5	TDir, NDir, ADir
Units		Drop-down: km, meters, miles, feet
Locality Type	Table 1	LCID, LCName, LCDescription; Instructions; Example
State		StateName, StateAbb, Uncertainty
County		CoName, Uncertainty
Museum Codes		Museum Name; 2-Digit Code; 3-4 Digit Code

Table Name	Table Reference	Notes
Type A	Table 2	SubType, Qualifier; Format Example; Uncertainty Estimate (m)
Transcriber		User Name
Rules		VB Scripting in Access
Alter Code	Table 4	Codes and definitions used to alter the GNIS table.

8.0 References

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